

Electrochemical Behaviour of Nitro-Derivatives of Benzene and Toluene in Various Solvents at Dropping Mercury Electrode

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The polarographic characteristics of nitro derivatives of benzene and toluene have been observed in aqueous mixtures of ethanol, acetonitrile and dimethyl-formamide (dmf) at Dropping Mercury Electrode (d.m.e.). All the measurements have been carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Polarographic characteristics have been examined in buffered as well as in unbuffered solutions. In buffered solution the Britton-Robinson buffer has been used, and the observations have been taken in the range of pH 2.9 to 11.0. While in case of unbuffered solutions, observations have been taken in different percentages (10, 30 and 50%) of solvents as mentioned above.

Our results indicate that meta-isomer reduces more easily than ortho and para-isomer. In ethanol in acidic pH ortho isomer has been reduced more difficultly than para-isomer, while in alkaline pH, the ortho isomer has been reduced more easily than para-isomer. The order of reduction $m > o > p$ in acetonitrile at acidic pH, $m > o > p$ in d.m.f. up to pH 4 and $m > p > o$ above pH 4, has been found. This suggests that the reduction is very much sensitive to pH of the solutions.

Diffusion current constants of the nitrotoluenes and nitrobenzene have been calculated from Ilkovic equation using drop time measured at same potential as the diffusion current. Difference in the values of diffusion current constants show the change in nature of electrode reaction. Values of slope indicate that the electrodes reaction is irreversible in nature and diffusion controlled in each case.

NITROBENZENE gives a four electron reduction wave at pH above 4, with the formation of phenylhydroxylamine. Below pH 5, an additional wave, at more cathodic potential with two electron reductions corresponds to further reduction of the intermediate phenylhydroxylamine to aniline¹ was reported.

Kolthoff and Lingane² reported the values obtained in buffers like (a) sodium acetate and hydrochloric acid, (b) potassium acid phthalate and hydrochloric acid and (c) sodium hydroxide and borax, containing 8% ethanol by volume. The values of slope, on plotting half-wave potentials against $\log i/i_a - i$ at various pH (0.075 at pH 2.5 and 0.088 at pH 9.2) were also reported³. The results obtained in 10% ethanol solutions were reported by Page, Smith and Waller⁴. Korshnunov and Kirillova⁵ reported the shift in half wave potentials with decrease in diffusion current by using 0.01% gelatin as maximum suppressor. B. Kastening⁶ reported the reduction of nitrobenzene in acetonitrile.

According to Kolthoff and Lingane, the nitrotoluenes behaves in a manner, similar to that of nitrobenzene. Pearson⁷ reported the values obtained in 8% ethanol for nitrotoluenes. Bennis, Powell and Astle⁸ reported the values of half-wave potentials in 50% ethanol, to be approximately 0.35V

more negative than in 8% ethanol. Field, Valle and Kane⁹ also reported the values of half-wave potentials in 80% dioxane solutions.

The polarographic behaviour of nitrobenzene and nitrotoluenes have not been carried out extensively in solvents like ethanol, acetonitrile and dimethylformamide (d.m.f) and in aqueous mixtures of these solvents. Investigations in buffer like Britton-Robinson have also not been studied.

The present work deals with the polarographic behaviour of nitrobenzene and nitrotoluenes in buffered aqueous mixtures of ethanol, acetonitrile and d. m. f. as well as in unbuffered solutions of these aqueous mixtures at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ C.

Experimental

All the polarographic measurements have been carried out with a manual set up. Polyflex galvanometer has been employed for recording current voltage curves. The dropping mercury electrode has the following characteristics, $m = 2.16$ mg/sec., $t = 3$ sec., in an open circuit and $h = 56.5$ cms.

Distillation of solvents has been carried out at different conditions; methyl-cyanide has been distilled over calcium hydride; dimethyl-formamide over anhydrous sodium carbonate under

reduced pressure and ethanol by simple distillation method.

Solutions of nitrobenzene and nitrotoluenes of 1mM concentration have been prepared at different pH (2.9 to 11.0) in different solvents. In the preparation of buffer solutions Britton-Robinson buffer has been used. Unbuffered solutions of 1mM concentration have also been prepared in different percentages of non-aqueous solvents. Supporting electrolyte, lithium perchlorate with ethanol and acetonitrile, while sodium perchlorate with dimethyl formamide have been used. These unbuffered solutions have been prepared at pH 7 ± 0.5 , 6 ± 0.1

and 6 ± 0.5 in aqueous mixtures of ethanol, acetonitrile and dimethylformamide respectively.

In all the experimental solutions 0.0015% triton-x-100 has been used as maximum suppressor. Presaturated and purified nitrogen gas has been bubbled through all experimental solutions to remove dissolved oxygen.

Results and Discussion

The polarographic data for nitrobenzene and nitrotoluenes in buffered and unbuffered solutions have been tabulated in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF 1 mM NITROTOLUENES IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS OF DIFFERENT pH

Sl. No.	pH	1. For <i>o</i> -nitrotoluene								
		10% aq. ethanol			10% aq. acetonitrile			10% aq. dmf.		
		$-E_{1/2}$ in volt	i_d (in μA)	Slope	$-E_{1/2}$ in volt	i_d (in μA)	Slope	$-E_{1/2}$ in volt	i_d (in μA)	Slope
1.	2.9	0.45	8.9208	0.1225	0.48	10.5592	0.1275	0.5775	10.110	0.1550
2.	4.6	0.62	10.1132	0.1575	0.61	10.5592	0.1425			
3.	5.6	0.7250	9.6972	0.1875	0.7075	9.5215	0.1525	0.73	11.151	0.1625
4.	7.3	0.7750	7.4340	0.1500	0.77	8.6264	0.13	0.80(a)	8.1774	0.14
								1.2150(b)	3.419	0.13
5.	9.0	0.85	6.9879	0.1200	0.8250	6.2745	0.0825	0.81(a)	6.9879	0.0950
								1.1550(b)	4.0143	0.1725
6.	11	0.9275	6.9879	0.1350	0.8825(a)	3.6426	0.0725	0.8550(a)	3.865	0.10
					1.1225(b)	3.5713	0.1250	1.0275(b)	5.2038	0.1375
2. For <i>m</i> -nitrotoluene										
1.	2.9	0.3875	9.3668	0.085	0.4250	11.8944	0.1125	0.4850	13.0095	0.1625
2.	4.6				0.55	12.4519	0.1275			
3.	5.6	0.56	8.6234	0.1150	0.6650	10.9651	0.1350	0.625	9.9942	0.1650
4.	7.3	0.70	8.7721	0.1225	0.7275	9.1066	0.1275	0.73(a)	7.8057	0.12
								1.1025(b)	2.7877	0.1424
5.	9.0	0.72	7.4340	0.0925	0.7725(a)	6.8764	0.0775	0.77(a)	5.2038	0.0775
					1.0325(b)	2.4460	0.0925	1.0550(b)	5.0179	0.13
6.	11	0.7950(a)	4.1630	0.1025	0.92	10.4072	0.2600	0.7850(a)	2.9736	0.0650
		1.0350(b)	3.5683	0.0750				1.0325(b)	7.434	0.1550
3. For <i>p</i> -nitrotoluene										
1.	2.9	0.44	11.7487	0.1450	0.5075	14.4963	0.1475	0.5925	12.985	0.1975
2.	4.6	0.56	10.8536	0.1425	0.6575	13.5970	0.20			
3.	5.6	0.6625	10.2619	0.14	0.7775	13.5970	0.1750	0.7025	12.4891	0.17
4.	7.3	0.7475	8.8751	0.1375	0.8325	10.9359	0.1375	0.7675(a)	9.3668	0.1350
								1.2225(b)	4.3117	0.0850
5.	9.0	0.78(a)	6.1258	0.0825	0.8575(a)	7.0623	0.1675	0.8025(a)	7.2853	0.1050
		1.1650(b)	4.7577	0.1625	1.26(b)	4.6462	0.1225	1.1750(b)	4.6090	0.1150
6.	11.0	0.8250(a)	4.6090	0.0875	0.9050(a)	5.2030	0.0925	0.830(a)	3.8656	0.0725
		1.0675(b)	5.3525	0.1750	1.3080(b)	8.1774	0.1750	1.23(b)	8.1774	0.1375
4. Polarographic Data of 1 mM Nitrobenzene at Different pH Indifference Solvent										
1.	3.	0.39(a)	12.2850	0.0925	0.55	11.5227	0.2100	0.4275	17.820	0.1225
		0.93(b)	3.730	0.2725						
2.	4.	0.5050(a)	15.130	0.1600	0.65	12.823	0.1875	0.60	15.795	0.2150
		1.3875(b)	3.105	0.1625						
3.	5.	0.5475	13.230	0.1775						
4.	6.	0.7075	12.2450	0.1475	0.6925(a)	12.082	0.1750	0.8(a)	12.420	0.1950
					1.0475(b)	1.8582	0.0925	1.2975(b)	3.105	0.1075
5.	7.							0.7875(a)	8.775	0.1325
								1.1675(b)	5.265	0.1075
6.	8.				0.7275(a)	7.8915	0.1025	0.7625(a)	8.100	0.0950
					1.0550(b)	3.3458	0.0975	1.1350(b)	9.450	0.1350
7.	9.							0.7900(a)	6.210	0.0875
								1.1450(b)	10.395	0.1450
8.	11.							0.7975(a)	4.590	0.0750
								1.13(b)	12.015	0.1475

(a) first wave, (b) second wave.

Upto pH 7.3 has been observed. Two distinct waves have been observed for *m*-nitrotoluene at pH 11 and for *p*-nitrotoluene at pH 9 and 11. In case where the two waves have been observed, the inflection is found at the middle of the total wave height. This indicates probably the unstable intermediate product nitroso-derivative, since the total number of electrons have been found to be four, corresponding to the final product, hydroxylamine derivative. The total wave height in single step reduction as well as in two step reduction has been found to be almost equal suggesting the possibility of the final product being the same in each case. The mechanism explaining the electrode reaction taking place due to the protonation and electron addition has been given as follows :

For nitrotoluenes, half-wave potentials increase with increasing pH of solution.

In unbuffered aqueous ethanol for nitrobenzene at different percentages of the solvent, a single wave has been obtained, corresponding to four electron reduction. For *o*-, and *m*-nitrotoluenes, a single wave, and for *p*-nitrotoluene, two waves have been observed. Mechanism has been suggested to be the same as in equation (I)

Observations (Acetonitrile as Solvent)

In buffered 10% aqueous acetonitrile, for nitrobenzene up to pH 4, *o*-nitrotoluene up to pH 9, *m*- and *p*-nitrotoluenes up to pH 7.3 a single wave has been observed in each case. The number of electrons have been calculated, to be four, corresponding to hydroxylamine derivative. For nitrobenzene above pH 4, *o*-nitrotoluene at pH 11 and *p*-nitrotoluene at pH 9 and 11, two separate waves have been observed. For *m*-nitrotoluene at pH 9 two waves have been observed but at pH 11 again a single wave has been observed. The mechanism for these reactions has been suggested to be as follows :

In the above mechanism the first, addition of electron and then protonation takes place.

In unbuffered solutions, for nitrobenzene in 10% aqueous acetonitrile a single wave and in 30 and 50% two distinct waves have been observed. The total wave height in two step reduction, and in single step reduction, has been found to be approximately same, suggesting the final product to be the same in each case. The number of electrons involved in the electrode mechanism have been found to be four corresponding to the formation of hydroxylamine derivative. For nitrotoluenes, two waves have been obtained in each case except for *m*-nitrotoluene in 10% aqueous acetonitrile, where a single wave has been obtained as shown in Table 2. The mechanism of electrode reaction has been suggested to be the same as in equation (V).

Observations (Dimethyl Formamide as Solvent)

For nitrobenzene in buffered 10% aqueous dimethylformamide at pH 3 and 4, a single wave has been obtained. Number of electrons have been found to be six, corresponding to the formation of aniline. Above pH 4, two distinct waves have been observed. The total wave height of these two waves have been found to be equal to the wave height of the single wave obtained upto pH 4. This suggests the final product to be the same in all cases. The height of first wave decreases and of the second wave increases with increasing pH of the solution as shown in Table 1. In acidic pH, aniline formation has taken place directly, while in alkaline conditions aniline has been formed as final product indirectly. Condensation reaction between phenylhydroxylamine and nitrosobenzene has taken place. Thus aniline has been formed through the intermediate azobenzene and hydrazobenzene as follows :

However in case of nitrotoluenes, in buffered 10% aqueous dimethylformamide a single wave has been observed, up to pH 5.6. At higher pH (7.3 to 11)

two distinct waves have been obtained. In these cases (pH 7.3 to 11) the wave height of first wave decreases and for second wave increases with increasing pH of the solution. The total number of electrons have been found to be four and the mechanism has been suggested to be the same as in equation (V).

Our results indicate that meta-isomer reduces more easily than ortho and para-isomers. In ethanol in acidic pH, ortho isomer has been reduced in more difficulty than para-isomer, while in alkaline pH, the ortho isomer has been reduced more easily than para isomer. The order of reduction $m > o > p$ in acetonitrile at acidic pH, $m > o > p$ in dimethylformamide up to pH 4 and $m > p > o$ above pH 4, has been found. This suggests that the reduction is very much sensitive to pH of solution.

On plotting half-wave potentials against pH, it has been observed that, half-wave potentials for first

wave increase while, for second decrease with increasing pH. However, for second wave of *p*-nitrotoluene in d.m.f. half-wave potentials have been found to be 1.2225V at pH 7.3, 1.1750V at pH 9.0 and 1.25V at pH 11.0. While in acetonitrile, for second wave of *p*-nitrotoluene, half-wave potentials at pH 11 is more negative than at pH 9 (At pH, 9, half-wave potential is 1.26V and at pH 11.0 it is 1.3080V). For nitrobenzene, for second wave, the half-wave potentials also increase with increasing pH in aqueous ethanol and acetonitrile while in case of d.m.f. for the first wave at pH 8, the half-wave potential has been found to be decreased.

Diffusion current constants of the nitrotoluenes and nitrobenzene (as listed in Table 3(a) and 3(b) respectively) have been calculated from Ilkovic equation using drop time measured at same potential as the diffusion current. Difference in the values of diffusion current constants show the change in nature of electrode reactions.

TABLE 3(a)—DIFFUSION CURRENT CONSTANTS OF NITROTOLUENES* ($i_d/cm^2 \text{ sec}^{1/2}$)

1. <i>o</i> -nitrotoluene						
Solvent	pH	pH	pH	pH	pH	pH
	2.9	4.6	5.6	7.3	9	11
10% aq. ethanol	4.7832	5.4226	5.1995	3.9860	3.746	3.746
10% aq. acetonitrile	5.6617	5.6617	5.10536	4.6254	3.8643	1.9531(a) 1.9149(b)
10% aq. d.m.f.	5.4209		5.9790	4.8846(a) 1.8332(b)	3.7463(a) 2.1527(b)	2.0723(a) 2.7902(b)
2. <i>m</i> -nitrotoluene						
10% aq. ethanol	5.0224		4.6238	4.7035	3.9860	2.2321(a) 1.9132(b)
10% aq. acetonitrile	6.3776	6.0766	5.8794	4.8828	3.6370(a) 1.3115(b)	5.5804
10% aq. d.m.f.	6.9756		5.9588	4.1853(a) 1.4947(b)	2.7902(a) 2.6905(b)	1.5944(a) 3.9860(b)
3. <i>p</i> -nitrotoluene						
10% aq. ethanol	6.2995	5.8196	5.5023	4.7587	3.2846(a) 2.5510(b)	2.4713(a) 2.8699(b)
10% aq. acetonitrile	7.7728	7.2906	7.2906	5.38117	3.7867(a) 2.4912(b)	2.7898(a) 4.384 (b)
10% aq. d.m.f.	6.935		6.6965	5.0224(a) 2.3119(b)	3.9063(a) 2.4713(b)	2.0727(a) 4.3846(b)

*Microamp./milli mole/mg^{1/2} sec^{1/2}, (a) first wave, (b) second wave.

TABLE 3(b)—DIFFUSION CURRENT CONSTANTS OF NITROTOLUENES AND NITROBENZENE

10% aq. ethanol	6.5871(a) 2.0268(b)	8.1072(a) 1.6648(b)	7.0938	6.5656			
10% aq. acetonitrile	6.1783	6.8756		6.4782(a) 0.9963(b)	4.2849(a) 1.7937(b)		
10% aq. d.m.f.	9.5549	8.4691		6.6597(a) 1.6648(b)	4.7050(a) 2.8230(b)	4.3431(a) 5.0670(b)	3.8297(a) 5.5737(b)
							2.4611(a) 6.4423(b)

(a) first wave,
(b) second wave.

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